

radiant

PROJECT

MS18 All tools and materials for Agrobiodiversity Toolbox ready

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Lead Beneficiary: UCP

Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** 30/06/2025
- **Actual submission date:** 25/06/2025
- **Project start date:** September 1st 2021
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Work package:** WP7
- **Work package leader:** CM
- **Milestone Title:** All tools and materials for Agrobiodiversity Toolbox ready

- **Mean of Verification**

A report including all tools and materials for the Agrobiodiversity Toolbox will be set, with a checklist to allow confirmation (Table 1).

1. Milestone description

In this milestone, we demonstrate that the new tools and platforms of the RADIANT project — including **RADIANT-LCA (WP4)**, **DSS (WP6)**, **the Agrobiodiversity Platform (DIH AGRI-FOOD) (WP6)**, **CropBASE-EU (WP1)**, **the Toolbox for quantifying ESs by farmers (WP3)**, **the e-RADIANT mobile app (WP1)**, and **the Policy Incentives Catalogue (WP5)**, **Practice Abstracts e-book (WP7)** — are made available in the **Agrobiodiversity Toolbox** via the **RADIANT website** as they are developed. Moreover, other important project materials will be made available via the Agrobiodiversity Toolbox to further ensure impact and project legacy. Further, the Agrobiodiversity Toolbox will be used as a portal for accessing and disseminating the activities and competencies of the European UC-Cluster.

2. Mean of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA? Yes

2.1. The Agrobiodiversity toolbox

The Agrobiodiversity toolbox was developed on the RADIANT website:

<https://www.radiantproject.eu/agrobiodiversity-toolbox/>.

2.2. Tools incorporated into the Agrobiodiversity toolbox

2.2.1. RADIANT APP (WP1)

An explanation of the **RADIANT APP (D1.7)**, along with a video and download links, has been made available in the **Agrobiodiversity Toolbox**. This resource aims to connect farmers with consumers, facilitate dialogue among value chain stakeholders, and promote education and awareness of Underutilised Crops (UCs).

2.2.2. CROPBASE-EU - Global knowledge base for Underutilised Crops (WP1)

An overview of the **CROPBASE-EU tool (D1.5 & D1.6)** and an educational video has been added to the **Agrobiodiversity Toolbox**. **CropBASE-EU** is an open-access global knowledge base designed to support the adoption of UCs in Europe. It integrates qualitative insights from local communities with quantitative data from scientific research to provide a comprehensive resource.

2.2.3. Policy Briefs & Policy Incentive Catalogue (WP5)

The **policy and governance recommendations** to promote the use of UCs throughout the value chain have been made available in the **Agrobiodiversity Toolbox** in the form of an **e-book of policy briefs (D5.5)**. These briefs address the barriers and lock-ins that UCs face within the current food system, outlining actionable steps to overcome these challenges. Additionally, the **Policy Incentive Catalogue (D5.6)** will be added to the toolbox in **M48**. Based on the initial policy scan, surveys with farmers and consumers, and new labelling practices, this comprehensive catalogue will detail all potential incentives to promote UCs.

2.2.4. The Agrobiodiversity Platform (WP6)

The **DIH AGRIFOOD Data Space (DADS)** is a federated **data-sharing platform** tailored for the agri-food sector (**D6.2**). DADS aims to **dismantle data silos across agriculture and food supply chains, promoting collaboration among farmers, processors, retailers, policymakers, and consumers**. The **link** for this platform has been added to the Agrobiodiversity Toolbox, and a link to the **D6.2** report for more comprehensive guidance on the functionalities and governance model.

2.2.5. Market Generator Avenue (MAG)- DSS (WP6)

A structured **decision support system (DSS)** has been developed in WP6 (**D6.3**). **MAG** (Market Avenue Generator) is an AI-powered DSS that helps users develop sustainable business models for innovations related to underutilised crops. It guides them through a structured

process that includes a lean canvas, a TRL assessment and a sustainability assessment, all on a single, user-friendly platform. A [link](#) to this tool and a guide manual [guide manual](#) has been added to the Agrobiodiversity toolbox.

2.2.6. RADIANT LCA (WP4)

The **RADIANT metrics (D4.5)**, including a **new attributional-LCA-based method** (e.g. incorporating ecosystem services or ecosystem functions), will be available in the Agrobiodiversity toolbox.

2.2.7. Toolbox for quantifying ESs by farmers (WP3)

The **APES Framework** (Agroecological Practices for Assessing Ecosystem Services) was developed to evaluate the environmental and societal contributions of UCs. This Ecosystem Services (ES) toolbox compiles indicators using a simple and rapid methodology to assess the ESs of the selected AURORA Farms and for **farmer's self-assessment of ESs (D3.3)**. It is linked to the deliberative choice experiments in T5.3, where farmers received information about ESs that could influence their stated preferences. The **APES toolkit** will be available in the Agrobiodiversity Toolbox.

2.2.8. Practice Abstracts e-book (WP7)

An **e-book** was developed with the **48 Practice Abstracts (D7.8 & D7.9)** developed during the RADIANT project and is now available in the Agrobiodiversity toolbox.

Table1. Agrobiodiversity Tools checklist.

Tools	Available	Available in M48
RADIANT APP (WP1)	Yes	-----
CROPBASE-EU (WP1)	Yes	-----
Policy Briefs (WP5)	Yes	-----
Policy Incentive Catalogue (WP5)	-----	Yes
Market Generator Avenue (WP6)	Yes	-----
DIH AGRIFOOD DATE SPACE (WP6)	Yes	-----
RADIANT - LCA (WP4)	-----	Yes
Toolbox for quantifying ESs by farmers (WP3)	-----	Yes
Practice Abstracts	-----	Yes